

IN SITU DAMAGE MECHANISMS INVESTIGATION OF POLYAMIDE/SHORT GLASS FIBER COMPOSITE

M.F. Arif¹, N. Despringre¹, Y. Chemisky¹, G. Robert², F. Meraghni^{1*}

¹LEM3, Arts et Métiers ParisTech, Metz, France, ²Solvay Engineering Plastics, Saint-Fons, France

* Corresponding author (fodil.meraghni@ensam.eu)

Keywords: *damage mechanisms, interfacial debonding, in situ test, microtomography, water absorption, humidity effect, glass transition temperature*

Abstract

In situ SEM damage mechanisms observation of injection molded polyamide-66/short glass fiber 30%wt composite (PA66/GF30) were performed under specimens conditioned at three different relative humidity conditions: RH=0%, 50% and RH=100%. X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) experiment on specimen with RH=0% was carried out for partial confirmation purpose. New damage chronologies were proposed. Damage initiation occurs at fiber ends and at locations where fibers are locally close to each other. The damage then further propagates through fiber-matrix interface. At high stress level, matrix transverse cracks (for RH=50% and 100% specimens) or fiber breakages (for RH=0% specimen) develop, leading to the damage accumulation and then to the final failure.

1 Introduction

Polyamide/short glass fiber composite (PA/GF) has been widely used in automotive industry due to its high strength-to-weight ratio and the ability of injection molding to produce complex parts. Particular challenge for the design of components made from this composite is the properties dependence of PA/GF due to the hydrophilic nature of the polyamide matrix. The polar amide groups generate strong attractions in the crystalline zone of the polyamide matrix, with hydrogen bonds being established between adjoining molecules. The water molecules can reduce these preexisting inter-chain hydrogen bonds and thus increases their chains mobility (plasticization effect) and volume (swelling effect) [1–4]. The plasticization effect decreases the glass transition temperature (T_g) of the polyamide matrix [5]. It also influences the mechanical properties of the polyamide matrix such as reduces

the strength and modulus while increasing the ductility [6]. The swelling effect the polyamide matrix induces mismatched fiber-matrix volumes expansion and thus creating a residual stress which in turn can reduce the fiber-matrix interfacial properties [7, 8]. The effect of environmental conditioning on the physical and mechanical properties of PA/GF has been studied by many researchers [1, 2, 5, 6, 9, 10]. However, so far no studies were focused on the effect of environmental conditions on the damage behavior of PA/GF.

The damage mechanisms in PA/GF has been studied by many researchers. Mouhmid et. al. [11] used acoustic emission and scanning electron microscopy (SEM) techniques to identify different types of damage in PA/GF. It was reported that the damage in PA/GF are characterized by matrix plasticization and microcracks, fiber pull out and fracture. In situ damage characterization of PA/GF by SEM technique has been performed by Sato [12] and it was reported that the damage starts from fiber ends and further propagates along the fiber/matrix interface. Afterwards, matrix shear band develops followed by crack growth. Horst et. al. [13, 14] and Barbouchi et. al. [10] studied the fatigue fracture surface of PA/GF and similar damage mechanisms as those proposed by Sato [12] for static loading were observed. X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) technique has been used to investigate the damage mechanisms in various composite materials [15–19]. Thanks to its inherent 3D analysis capability, though careful data treatments are needed such as to resolve the lower resolution of μ CT voxel as compared to the damage size and the presence of artifacts [19–21].

The study of the physical aspects of damage mechanisms is important in order to develop a more reliable and accurate modeling of their effects to

predict the overall mechanical behavior of the composite. Based on authors knowledge, so far no material model developed for PA/GF that integrate the physics of damage mechanisms in terms of its initiation and kinetic, such as the model developed by Nouri et. al. that use a phenomenological approach to consider the damage [22–24] or the micromechanics model developed by Kammoun et. al. that consider the damage by determining a certain damage threshold value based on failure criteria [25].

In this work, in situ SEM damage mechanisms observation of injection molded polyamide-66/short glass fiber 30%wt composite (PA66/GF30) were investigated under specimens that have been conditioned at 23°C and three different relative humidity conditions: RH=0%, 50% and RH=100%. The RH=0%, 50% and 100% specimens represented the conditions where the composites are respectively in glassy, transition and rubbery zones, according to its T_g values [26, 27]. For the confirmation purpose, the results of our first μ CT experimental campaign on the RH=0% specimen will be presented. The experimental results showed that higher RH exhibited higher damage level. Moisture content variation led to different damage behavior. A better understanding of the damage mechanisms taking into account the environmental conditions shall contribute to a better formulation of local damage criteria and thus to include with a higher accuracy the physical modeling of their effects to predict the overall mechanical behavior of the composite integrating the damage initiation and evolution.

2 Material description and Microstructure

The material for this study is PA66/GF30 supplied by Solvay Engineering Plastics - France, under the trade name of Technyl® A 218 V30. The material is presented in the form of a rectangular plate with the thickness of 3.2 mm. The material was prepared by compounding the polyamide pellets and glass fibers in a twin-screw extruder. Subsequently, the resulting PA66/GF30 compound was transferred into an injection molding machine.

This material has a specific microstructure characterized by a well-defined skin-shell-core layer formation, typical of thermoplastic composites manufactured by injection molding process [28–30]. As described in Fig. 1, around 90% of fibers were

formed at the shell layer with global fiber orientation longitudinal to the mold flow direction (MFD). The core layer constituted about 5% of fibers with the global fiber orientation perpendicular to the MFD. The random skin layer is formed at the area in direct contact with the mold wall. The thickness of the skin layer constituted about 5% of fibers, considering both the upper and lower skin layers. Although the random skin layer was developed, the fibers in this layer seemed to have tendency to orient to the MFD. The quantitative analysis of the degree of randomness will be addressed in our next work. This formation of skin-shell-core layer only occurred through the thickness of the material and no microstructure heterogeneity was found through the width and length of the specimen.

Mostly, the fibers orient parallel to the shear flow direction. The shear flow exists at the zone near to the wall due to the friction between the polymer melt and mold wall, whereas the shear flow is zero in the core zone due to the absence of mold wall friction influence. This leads fibers oriented parallel to MFD at the shell zone and oriented perpendicular to MFD at the core zone. A thin random layers were formed due to the polymer melt that is in direct contact with the relatively cold temperature of the mold wall and thus fibers freeze without any preferential orientations [28].

3 Experimental procedure

3.1 Preparation of specimens

The testing specimens were machined in longitudinal direction to the MFD from a rectangular bar produced by injection molding. The specimen dimension of 45x10x3.2 mm³ was chosen. In situ observations were carried out at specimens with equilibrium moisture content after being conditioned at room temperature (23°C) and different relative humidity: RH=0%, 50% and 100%. The sample with RH=0% was obtained by putting the specimen after polishing inside a vacuum oven at 80°C for 15h to ensure zero moisture content in the whole sample. The specimen then was metalized with gold prior observations. An accelerated conditioning method was used to obtain the equilibrium water uptake equivalent to that in 23°C, RH=50% and 100%. The RH=50% specimen was prepared according to ISO 1110 standard by putting the specimen inside a weathering chamber at 70°C and RH=62% until a

constant weight was obtained. The procedure was continued by one week specimen conditioning at 23°C, RH=50% in order to make homogenous and equilibrium water concentrations in the whole sample. Subsequently, the specimen was sputtered with a thin layer of gold prior observations. The specimen with RH=100% was obtained by immersing the sample in a boiling water for 35h and then continued by room temperature water immersion for one week. The polishing of RH=100% specimen was performed after the boiling water immersion and the gold metallization was conducted right before the in situ observation.

3.2 In Situ bending test and observations

In situ observations were performed by subjecting the specimens into a flexural load using a three-point bending micro-machine (27 mm of span length) assembled inside a scanning electron microscope (SEM) device. The load was increased with a crosshead speed of 400 μ m/min and stopped for a moment at many levels of stress for microscopic in situ observation and images acquisition. The observation time during the halt was limited to around 3 minutes to reduce relaxation effect of the composite. The observation was performed through the surface thickness of the composite with particular emphasize at the outermost tensile region of the specimen. Thanks to the three-point bending flexural system that allows a maximum stress at the outermost region so that the expected damage zones can be predicted.

3.3 X-ray micro-computed tomography (μ CT) observation

For a confirmation purpose of the in situ SEM observations, μ CT technique was employed to study the damage mechanisms of longitudinal specimen of PA66/GF30 that has been subjected into a tensile loading till failure. The μ CT experiment was performed at the beam line ID19 of the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) in Grenoble, France [31]. The voxel resolution of the ID19 system was 1.4 μ m. The μ CT experiment was performed on the sample with the size of 2 x 2 x 3.2 mm³ extracted from the tensile loaded specimen. In this work, the μ CT test was limited to our first experimental campaign for the specimen with RH=0%.

4 Results and Analysis

4.1 Effect of RH on the mechanical properties

The normalized load vs. displacement graph from the result of bending tests is presented in Fig. 2. Based on the graph, one can compute the flexural stress and strain according to ISO 178 standard. After reducing the clearance effect of the testing device at the early loading phase, one can deduce that the flexural strength and modulus of PA66/GF30 decreased with the increase of RH. The plasticization effect and the decrease of interfacial properties due to water absorption could be the contributing factors for the decrease of flexural strength and modulus of PA66/GF30. In fact, the RH=0%, 50% and 100% specimens represented the conditions where the composites are respectively in glassy ($T_g > T_{room}$), transition ($T_g \approx T_{room}$) and rubbery zones ($T_g < T_{room}$) [26, 27]. The obvious differences noticed on the strength and modulus of PA66/GF30 by the variation of RH could be due to this factor. Basically, plasticization increases the elongation to failure of the polyamide matrix and hence the composite. As shown in Fig. 2, specimens with RH=50% and 100% displayed higher elongation to failure than that of RH=0 specimen, whereas no significant difference was observed between the one at RH=50% and 100%. This trend is the same as the result reported by Akay [32]. While the increase of elongation to failure due to higher RH is clear for pure polyamide 66, this phenomena is sometimes not evident for fiber reinforced composite materials.

4.2 Damage initiation and propagation mechanisms

The initial condition of microstructure is shown in Fig. 3 which detects no damage. As the load increased, the damage started to develop. As described in Fig. 4a, the damage initiations in the form of interfacial debonding were found at two locations, at fiber ends and at the locations where fibers are close to each other. These configurations generate local stress concentrations which could initiate the damage. As the load increased, the damage then propagated along the fiber-matrix interface. As shown in Fig. 4b, the propagations occurred both through the in-plane and out-of-plane directions. This propagation mechanism was valid for all specimens with different RH.

4.3 Matrix transverse cracks and fiber breakages at high stress level

At high stress level, two mechanisms were observed, matrix transverse cracking and fiber breakage. Transverse cracks were observed at RH=50% and 100% specimens, while fiber breakages were observed frequently at RH=0% specimens (Fig. 5). Subsequently, these mechanisms lead to the damage accumulation and then to the composite final failure. Further discussion about the effect of RH will be presented in the following subsection.

4.4. Effect of RH on the damage behavior

Damage behavior differences due to the effect of moisture content of the composite were observed. Consistent results were found regarding to the qualitative observation of the number of damaged zone on the composites surface which shows that the higher RH resulted in higher damage level. For RH=0% specimen where the water content is nearly zero (<0.2%), damage level was very small. The damage was notably in the form of interfacial decohesion. At high stress level, fiber breakages were detected (Fig. 5a). As the specimen exhibits good interfacial properties due to the absence of water content, the remaining weak point of the composite is the fiber. Theoretically, glass fiber possesses high tensile properties. However, due to local configuration of fibers inside the composite, the local stress level may exceed the ultimate strength of the fiber and thus fiber breakage take place.

For RH=100% specimen, the damage level was high. The damage was dominated by high number interfacial debondings and matrix transverse crackings at high stress level, as shown in Fig. 5c. The RH=50% specimen exhibited many interfacial decohesions, the same as that in RH=100% specimen, although the damage level of RH=50% specimen was evidently lower than that of RH=100% specimen. While the transverse cracks at RH=50% specimen were only possible at locations where fibers relatively close to each other (Fig. 5b), the transverse cracks of RH=100% specimen were found independent of local fiber configurations (Fig. 5c). Matrix shear bands were observed frequently at RH=100% specimen (Fig. 5c and 6), while this occurrence was not evident for RH=50% specimen. This could be due to the high plasticization effect of

RH=100% specimen so that the localized plastic deformations and possibly the transverse cracks are prominent.

4.5. Damage mechanisms observed by μ CT

Damage mechanisms in PA66/GF30 composite with RH=0% were observed by μ CT method. The specimen was subjected to a tensile loading, which possesses the same loading as the outermost tensile region of the bending load. As shown in Fig. 7, interfacial decohesions and fiber breakage were evidenced, which is identical with the results of in situ SEM observation.

5 Damage mechanisms chronology

Based on the results of in situ bending tests, the overall damage scenarios can be constructed. Fig. 8 shows sequential images of the RH=100% specimen from its initial state to the stress level right before the final failure. This image can be used to construct an idea how the damage evolves with the increase of load, especially for the RH=50% and 100% specimens since both RH levels exhibited almost the same damage behavior, although the damage level between the two is different.

The damage mechanisms chronology of PA66/GF30 can be summarized as follow:

- a) Damage initiation occurs at fiber ends and at the locations where fibers are locally close to each other.
- b) Damage propagation happens through interfacial debonding growth
- c) At high stress level, matrix transverse crackings (for RH=50% and 100% specimens), or fiber breakages (for RH=0% specimen) develop. These will eventually lead to damage accumulation and then to the composite final failure.

6 Summary

The damage scenarios for PA66/GF30 with variation of RH have been identified and analyzed. Results showed that higher RH exhibited higher damage level. New damage chronologies were proposed. Damage initiation occurs at fiber ends and at the locations where fibers are locally close to each other. The damage then further propagates through the fiber-matrix interface. At high stress level, matrix transverse crackings (for RH=50% and 100% specimens) or fiber breakages (for the RH=0%

specimen) develop, leading to the damage accumulation and then to the final failure. The experimental findings on physical aspect of damage are of importance for identifying local damage criteria that would be implemented into a predictive micromechanical model [33]. To this end, the multi-scale model would be extended to integrate fiber-matrix interface damage kinetic coupled with the viscous rheology of the polyamide matrix in relation with PA66/GF30 composite material microstructure.

References

- [1] A. Bergeret, L. Ferry, and P. Jenny, "Influence of the fibre/matrix interface on ageing mechanisms of glass fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites (PA-6,6, PET, PBT) in a hygrothermal environment," *Polymer Degradation and Stability*, vol. 94, no. 9, pp. 1315–1324, 2009.
- [2] A. Bergeret, I. Pires, M. P. Foulc, B. Abadie, L. Ferry, and A. Crespy, "The hygrothermal behaviour of glass-fibre-reinforced thermoplastic composites: a prediction of the composite lifetime," *Polymer Testing*, vol. 20, no. 7, pp. 753–763, 2001.
- [3] I. Carrascal, J. A. Casado, J. A. Polanco, and F. Gutiérrez-Solana, "Absorption and diffusion of humidity in fiberglass-reinforced polyamide," *Polymer Composites*, vol. 26, no. 5, pp. 580–586, 2005.
- [4] L. Monson, M. Braunwarth, and C. W. Extrand, "Moisture absorption by various polyamides and their associated dimensional changes," *Journal of Applied Polymer Science*, vol. 107, no. 1, pp. 355–363, 2008.
- [5] A. Hassan, N. A. Rahman, and R. Yahya, "Moisture absorption effect on thermal, dynamic mechanical and mechanical properties of injection-molded short glass-fiber/polyamide 6,6 composites," *Fibers and Polymers*, vol. 13, no. 7, pp. 899–906, 2012.
- [6] N. Jia, H. a. Fraenkel, and V. a. Kagan, "Effects of Moisture Conditioning Methods on Mechanical Properties of Injection Molded Nylon 6," *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, vol. 23, no. 7, pp. 729–737, 2004.
- [7] W. L. Bradley and T. S. Grant, "The effect of the moisture absorption on the interfacial strength of polymeric matrix composites," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 30, no. 21, pp. 5537–5542, 1995.
- [8] L. Gautier, B. Mortaigne, and V. Bellenger, "Interface damage study of hydrothermally aged glass-fibre-reinforced polyester composites," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 59, no. 16, pp. 2329–2337, 1999.
- [9] D. Valentin, F. Paray, and B. Guetta, "The hygrothermal behaviour of glass fibre reinforced Pa66 composites: A study of the effect of water absorption on their mechanical properties," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 46–56, 1987.
- [10] S. Barbouchi, V. Bellenger, A. Tcharkhtchi, P. Castaing, and T. Jollivet, "Effect of water on the fatigue behaviour of a pa66/glass fibers composite material," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 42, no. 6, pp. 2181–2188, 2007.
- [11] B. Mouhmid, A. Imad, N. Benseddiq, S. Benmedakhène, and A. Maazouz, "A study of the mechanical behaviour of a glass fibre reinforced polyamide 6,6: Experimental investigation," *Polymer Testing*, vol. 25, no. 4, pp. 544–552, 2006.
- [12] N. Sato, T. Kurauchi, S. Sato, and O. Kamigaito, "Microfailure behaviour of randomly dispersed short fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites obtained by direct SEM observation," *Journal of Materials Science*, vol. 26, no. 14, pp. 3891–3898, 1991.
- [13] J. J. Horst and J. L. Spoomaker, "Fatigue fracture mechanisms and fractography of short-glassfibre-reinforced polyamide 6," *Journal of materials science*, vol. 32, no. 14, pp. 3641–3651, 1997.
- [14] J. J. Horst and J. L. Spoomaker, "Mechanisms of fatigue in short glass fiber reinforced polyamide 6," *Polymer Engineering & Science*, vol. 36, no. 22, pp. 2718–2726, 1996.
- [15] L. Babout, E. Maire, J.-Y. Buffière, and R. Fougères, "Characterization by X-ray computed tomography of decohesion, porosity growth and coalescence in model metal matrix composites," *Acta Materialia*, vol. 49, no. 11, pp. 2055–2063, 2001.
- [16] C. Chateau, L. Gélébart, M. Bornert, J. Crépin, E. Boller, C. Sauder, and W. Ludwig, "In situ X-ray microtomography characterization of damage in SiCf/SiC minicomposites," *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 71, no. 6, pp. 916–924, 2011.
- [17] E. Maire, L. Babout, J.-Y. Buffière, and R. Fougères, "Recent results on 3D characterisation of microstructure and damage of metal matrix composites and a metallic foam using X-ray tomography," *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 319–321, pp. 216–219, 2001.
- [18] G. P. McCombe, J. Rouse, R. S. Trask, P. J. Withers, and I. P. Bond, "X-ray damage characterisation in self-healing fibre reinforced polymers," *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 43, no. 4, pp. 613–620, 2012.
- [19] F. Cosmi and A. Bernasconi, "Micro-CT investigation on fatigue damage evolution in short

- fibre reinforced polymers,” *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 79, pp. 70–76, 2013.
- [20] M. Krause, J.-M. Hausherr, and W. Krenkel, “(Micro)-Crack detection using local Radon transform,” *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 527, no. 26, pp. 7126–7131, 2010.
- [21] P. J. Withers and M. Preuss, “Fatigue and Damage in Structural Materials Studied by X-Ray Tomography,” *Annual Review of Materials Research*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 81–103, Aug. 2012.
- [22] H. Nouri, F. Meraghni, and P. Lory, “Fatigue damage model for injection-molded short glass fibre reinforced thermoplastics,” *International Journal of Fatigue*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 934–942, 2009.
- [23] F. Meraghni, H. Nouri, N. Bourgeois, C. Czarnota, and P. Lory, “Parameters identification of fatigue damage model for short glass fiber reinforced polyamide (PA6-GF30) using digital image correlation,” *Procedia Engineering*, vol. 10, pp. 2110–2116, 2011.
- [24] H. Nouri, C. Czarnota, and F. Meraghni, “Experimental Parameters Identification of Fatigue Damage Model for Short Glass Fiber Reinforced Thermoplastics GFRP,” in *Design and Modeling of Mechanical Systems*, M. Haddar, L. Romdhane, J. Louati, and A. Ben Amara, Eds. Berlin, Heidelberg: Springer Berlin Heidelberg, 2013, pp. 523–530.
- [25] S. Kammoun, I. Doghri, L. Adam, G. Robert, and L. Delannay, “First pseudo-grain failure model for inelastic composites with misaligned short fibers,” *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, vol. 42, no. 12, pp. 1892–1902, 2011.
- [26] A. Launay, Y. Marco, M. H. Maitournam, and I. Raoult, “Modelling the influence of temperature and relative humidity on the time-dependent mechanical behaviour of a short glass fibre reinforced polyamide,” *Mechanics of Materials*, vol. 56, pp. 1–10, 2013.
- [27] A. Hassan, N. M. Salleh, R. Yahya, and M. R. K. Sheikh, “Fiber length, thermal, mechanical, and dynamic mechanical properties of injection-molded glass-fiber/polyamide 6,6: plasticization effect,” *Journal of Reinforced Plastics and Composites*, vol. 30, no. 6, pp. 488–498, 2011.
- [28] A. Bernasconi, P. Davoli, A. Basile, and A. Filippi, “Effect of fibre orientation on the fatigue behaviour of a short glass fibre reinforced polyamide-6,” *International Journal of Fatigue*, vol. 29, no. 2, pp. 199–208, 2007.
- [29] B. Klimkeit, S. Castagnet, Y. Nadot, A. El Habib, G. Benoit, S. Bergamo, C. Dumas, and S. Achard, “Fatigue damage mechanisms in short fiber reinforced PBT+PET GF30,” *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, vol. 528, no. 3, pp. 1577–1588, 2011.
- [30] B. Mlekusch, “Fibre orientation in short-fibre-reinforced thermoplastics II. Quantitative measurements by image analysis,” *Composites science and technology*, vol. 59, pp. 547–560, 1999.
- [31] www.esrf.eu/UsersAndScience/Experiments/Imaging/ID19.
- [32] M. Akay, “Moisture absorption and its influence on the tensile properties of glass-fibre reinforced polyamide 6,6,” *Polymers and Polymer Composites*, vol. 2, no. 6, pp. 349–354, 1994.
- [33] Z. Jendli, F. Meraghni, J. Fitoussi, and D. Baptiste, “Multi-scales modelling of dynamic behaviour for discontinuous fibre SMC composites,” *Composites Science and Technology*, vol. 69, no. 1, pp. 97–103, 2009.

Fig. 1. Skin-shell-core microstructure formation developed through the thickness of the composite due to the injection molding process.

Fig. 2. Normalized load vs. displacement curve of PA66/GF30 specimens with variation of relative humidity

Fig. 3. Virgin surface of PA66/GF30 specimen

Fig. 4. PA66/GF30, RH=50% specimen, a) damage initiation at 30% σ_f , b) damage propagation at 83% σ_f (σ_f = flexural strength)

Fig. 5. PA66/GF30 specimen, a) fiber breakage at 95% σ_f of RH=0%, b) matrix transverse cracks at 98% σ_f of RH=50%, c) matrix transverse crackings and shear bands at 98% σ_f of RH=100% (σ_f = flexural strength)

Fig. 6. Shear band at 98% σ_f of PA66/GF30, RH=100% specimen (σ_f =flexural strength)

Fig. 7. Fiber breakage and interfacial decohesions of PA66/GF30 observed by μ CT

Fig. 8. Image sequences representing the damage evolution of PA66/GF30, RH=100% under bending load from the virgin state to the stage prior to the failure. a) Virgin state - b) 30% σ_f - c) 55% σ_f - d) 75% σ_f - e) 90% σ_f - f) 99% σ_f (σ_f = flexural strength)